

B1301

Conditioning optimization in Sandvik Sanergy® HT 441 after the forming process

Pablo Collantes-Jiménez, Carlos Bernuy-López, Ulf Bexell, Jörgen Westlinder
Surface Research, Strategic Research, AB Sandvik Materials Technology
81181 Sandviken/Sweden

Contact authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

Stainless steel-based interconnects for Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) are essential parts in obtaining competitive devices. Pre-coated stainless steels can be produced in a roll-to-roll process and large volumes, which reduce the cost of interconnect fabrication. The cost-effective AISI 441 ferritic stainless steel grade can be used with a Ce/Co nanocoating in order to form a protective spinel oxide layer. This material is manufactured by Sandvik Materials Technology under the name Sandvik Sanergy® HT 441. Mechanical stresses during fabrication of an interconnect causes microcracks in the coating exposing the substrate material which can impact the oxidation behaviour negatively. Despite this, the metal coating experiences a volume expansion when the oxide scale is formed. This enables to cover the areas where there is no coating present and protecting them in what is called the 'self-healing' effect.

The aim of the present study is to provide insights about how several pre-oxidation treatments influence the self-healing properties of the cracks generated in the coating in as-formed state. This includes the analysis of microstructural and chemical changes in order to obtain the best recipe for pre-oxidation. Thus, different series of temperature (isochronous and isothermal from 600 to 850 °C) and several pre-treatments times (1 h to 24 h) were tested. The same area was carefully marked (figure 1) and followed by means of SEM surface characterization and chemical analysis in order to follow the same crack distribution area. The results from this work indicate that an adequate self-healing of the material can be achieved within short times using isothermal pre-treatments at temperatures over 750 °C.

Introduction

Materials based on ferritic stainless steels and high chromium alloys are cost-effective materials for SOFC interconnects [1-4]. The TEC matches closely the one of the electrodes and electrolytes with the benefit of higher toughness and strength. In addition, the implementation of protective coatings is an effective solution in order to mitigate the chromium vaporization issue in this technology and also avoid high corrosion resistance [1]. Surface layers of Reactive Element Oxides (REOs), rare earth perovskites and composite spinel oxides have shown good properties to reduce oxide growth kinetics, increase oxide scale conductivity and improve oxide scale-to-metal adhesion [2]. The combination of composite layers of REOs (Ce, La, Y) and composite spinels of the Mn-Co system effectively reduce the high-temperature oxidation rate [3] while still retaining high conductivity and reducing chromium evaporation [4].

Coatings such as Ce/Co can be deposited in metallic state with techniques such as Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) [6] in a continuous roll-to-roll process [5]. The metallic pre-coating withstands the forming operations without spalling [5]. After forming, the pre-coating is oxidized at high temperatures and reacts with the Mn diffusing from the steel, generating the desired final (Co,Mn)₃O₄ spinel coating [7, 8] over a seed layer of Cerium oxide. It has been observed that the forming operations can crack the surface of the pre-coating exposing the substrate materials, eliminating the protection against Cr-evaporation.

Nevertheless, previous studies have shown that the micrometer size cracks can be self-healed at high temperatures due to the instant volume expansion of the coating as it oxidizes [9]. In order to make SOFC cost-effective and commercially attractive, longer service lives of the materials are needed to decrease the cost per kWh. An important cost lowering factor is process optimization and devise new operating conditions (temperatures and times) that can help to obtain durable materials in scalable production ways.

The purpose of this work is to obtain knowledge about the self-healing properties of the interconnect. Coatings like Ce/Co produce a protective layer that effectively stops chromia evaporation by different mechanisms. With increased temperatures, some elements in the steel substrate can be diffused outwards and form different oxides when combined with the elements in the coating. These oxides experience a volume expansion that is able to cover the exposed areas in the material where there is no coating present, protecting them in what is called the 'self-healing' effect. Although previous studies (5, 9, 10) have shown that this mechanism is effective in pre-treatments at high temperature (>800°C), investigations about the effect of self-healing properties at medium to low temperatures are limited and, therefore, a systematic study varying temperature and time is performed and evaluated by SEM techniques.

1. Experiments

1.1 Materials and Sample preparation

The material for analysis was a ferritic stainless steel Sandvik Sanergy® HT 441, which incorporates a coating of Ce/Co with thickness below 1 µm. [11]. It was deposited in metallic state using a Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) roll-to-roll process in Sandvik Material Technology AB. Prior to this study, Sandvik Sanergy® 441 HT samples were obtained in the form of 20 cm² sheets by 0.3 mm in thickness and they were submitted to the modified Erichsen test. An initial circumference of 5 cm in diameter was marked on top of the surface, and the sheet was punched until a 12% biaxial deformation (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Sample obtention and marking prior exposure and SEM characterization

1.2 Pre-oxidation exposure

Information was needed for a vast array of the possible conditionings depending on time and temperature presented in Table 1. The treatments were grouped in two experimental sets to simulate different manufacturing conditions, isothermal and isochronous. Three series of isothermal pre-oxidation treatments and another three isochronous were designed. A sample was assigned to each of the series. To be able to study the properties in the same area, the experiments had to be performed alternating analysis and treatment.

Table 1: Pre-oxidation treatment matrix

T/t	AS FORMED	1h	5h	24h
600	A0	A1	A3	A5
750	D0	D1	D3	D5
850	F0	F1	F3	F5

For every treatment, the heating and cooling ramps were set to 5 °C/min. A Type K thermocouple connected to a Data Logger TC-08 was installed next to the sample to performed on-line temperature measurements.

1.3. Analytical methods

The analysis process and the exposures were conducted in alternate stages synchronously. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used for both imaging and chemical analysis with Energy Dispersive x-ray Spectroscopy (EDS). A Zeiss EVO 50 VP scanning electron microscope has been used in this research. The samples were fixed in a disk holder which was set perpendicular to the beam. The accelerating voltage was set to 20 keV and the probe current was adjusted between 160 and 900 pA. The working distance was set to 10 or 11 mm and kept constant within the series.

2. Results

2.1 Cracks Development Analysis Through SEM Imaging

The morphological evolution of the oxides on the coating and the substrate (open cracks) was evaluated before and after the treatments by top-down SEM. The image acquisition was performed in a small area next to the scriber mark for reference.

2.1.1. Isothermal treatments

Figure 2 presents an overview of all isothermal treatments. A considerable spread in the crack size can be observed at 600 °C. After 1 h, signs of oxidation were already visible which effectively close the small cracks ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$). However, it remained unsuccessful for achieving complete self-healing. Spallation could be seen in some of the coating oxide scales. After 5 h and even 24 h of exposure, none appreciable differences were observed. The features observed in the center of the images were identified as impurities coming from the cutting process.

The magnitude of the average crack width in the 750 °C series was slightly greater than in the 600 °C one. After 1 h, the sample surface exhibited submicron crack closure as a result of the volume expansion. The medium size cracks of 1 to 2 μm were also reduced to a great extent. Spallation was not observed on the coating. After 5 hours of treatment a similar crack size and healing characteristics on the coating was observed. However, a substantial difference in the morphology of the sample was observed after 24 h. The precipitates on the coating kept growing in size and began to cover the surface homogeneously. At the same time, the growth of precipitates of the same structure on the substrate surface was observed.

The same crack size distribution already seen for the other samples is observed for the 850 °C series. A similar development as the 750 °C series was observed but with a quicker development thanks to the increased treatment temperature. After 1 h the volume expansion of the oxidized coating covered the sub-micron cracks, with extended effect after 5 h. An advanced state of self-healing effect is observed after 24 hours. The surface is completely covered with coarse precipitates (up to 2 μm) and there is almost no distinction between the coating and the exposed areas anymore.

Figure 2: Overview of the top-down SEM images of the crack tracking analysis for all isothermal treatments.

2.1.2. Isochronous treatments

Figure 3 presents an overview of all isochronous treatments. After 1 h of the isochronous series, comparable features to all the samples can be observed. The largest ($> 2 \mu\text{m}$) cracks present in the as-formed state are not healed completely even at high temperatures. A very small effect in the healing was appreciated by volume expansion.

Increasing the length of the isochronous treatment to 5 h did not result in substantial differences in the morphology. Small micrometric cracks heal as an effect of the immediate volume expansion in the same way as observed before. However, some signs of spallation in the coating edges at the bottom left side which remained through all further steps. Despite the closure of minor size cracks, the largest ones ($> 2 \mu\text{m}$) remained unhealed even at high temperatures.

The development of the morphology and phases was the most distinct for the 24 h series. However, only the samples exposed at higher temperatures, i.e. $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ shows a full self-healing of the cracks. At $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ only smaller cracks were healed although the effect is considerably larger than for lower isochronous treatments.

Figure 3: Overview of the top-down SEM images of the crack tracking analysis for all isochronous treatments

2.2 Oxide Growth Through EDS analysis

Previous data showed the effectiveness of the isothermal treatments as an effective solution for increasing the self-healing and therefore, deeper EDS analysis for the series at 750 and $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were performed.

2.2.1. Isothermal series at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 4 I presents the obtained spectra on the selected area of the crack. The most representative elements in the formation of protective coatings of ferritic steel interconnects are represented in the table of the figure. Their composition is given in atomic per cent to give information about the oxide stoichiometry. The analysis areas through the different exposures are marked in red in the images. Data collected from

Figure 4 I a in the as-formed state shows that only iron and chromium were detected. This shows a very similar proportion to the average composition of the steel. Co was detected from the first-hour treatment in the area of analysis of Figure 4 I b. At longer treatment times, the selected spot in Figure 4 I c indicates that the composition of the newly formed oxides was rich in Mn and Co.

The corresponding analysis of the coating is seen in Figure 4 II. The obtained data from Figure 4 II a revealed the presence of Cr and Fe in the coating in the as-formed state composition. The atomic content of Fe, Co, Cr and O remained stable in the analysis from the areas in Figure 4 II b to d. It should be noted that in Figure 4 II c, the analysis area selected was of the opposite side of the crack.

Figure 4: Oxide growth on the crack I) and on the coating II) surface by EDS analysis in the 750 °C isothermal series at a) as formed, b) 1 h, c) 5 h and d) 24 h. The measurement area can be seen in e) and the atomic composition in the table directly below.

2.2.2. Isothermal series at 850 °C.

The as-formed F0 sample from these series was not analysed since the composition of crack and coating was determined in D0 from the previous series. Both samples were belonging to the same piece of material in the untreated state.

Figure 5 I presents the EDS analysis through different stages of isothermal treatments at 850 °C in the crack area. The red ellipse in Figure 5 I d delimits where the EDS was obtained. The embedded table in Figure 5 I shows that all representative elements are visible in the analysis from the first stage in the treatments. Furthermore, it depicts a steady increase of Cr, Mn and Co content through the treatments in Figure 5 I.

The analysis of the coating is presented in Figure 5 II. As can be seen in the table the trends are comparable to what was seen in Figure 5 II. Between Figure 5 II a and b, there is not a large difference in Cr content, but it is double in Figure 5 II c. The increase is even more pronounced in the Mn content. Co content is steadily decreased during the treatments. Mn is found in the coating in Figure 5 II d in the same proportion as in the crack in Figure 5 I.

Figure 5: Oxide growth on the crack I) and the coating II) surface by EDS analysis in the 850 °C isothermal series at a) 1 h, b) 5 h and c) 24 h. The measurement area can be seen in d) and the atomic composition in the table directly below.

3. Discussions

3.1. Influence of pre-oxidation treatment design on the self-healing properties

The ability to develop a protective and homogeneous oxide layer that protects the substrate against chromia evaporation is the greatest factor in self-healing properties [5, 2, 7, 12]. Having a general view over the isothermal treatments in Figure 2 it is possible to observe some trends. It is appreciable that an instant volume expansion of the coating covered effectively the smaller submicrometric cracks regardless of the treatment temperature. Besides, the morphology of the precipitates on the coating is appreciably changed during the series. On the other hand, Figure 2 b to d showed a big effect of spallation in low-temperature series that was not so pronounced in higher temperatures. Ultimately, higher temperature treatments were considerably regarded to be more effective in achieving self-healing properties and to display higher levels of homogenization within shorter periods of time.

Previous studies from Froitzheim et al. [7] have reported that the process of oxidation of a metallic cobalt coating of similar thickness is produced within the first 30 seconds of the exposure. In that time, most of the cobalt coating is stratified in a double layer of Co_3O_4 oxide formed at the surface while CoO is found in the inner part. Froitzheim et al. also observed that after an hour of treatment at 800 °C, the oxidation to Co_3O_4 is completed, and the volume increases. Bridging the gap with the present study, the volume expansion in the coating observed after the first hours of treatment is most probably related to that transformation.

The deformation process in the as-formed state does not seem to affect the adhesion properties of the scales. However, Figure 2 b and f show that the edges of some scales are spalled-off in the first hour of treatments at 600 °C and 750 °C respectively. Scale spallation has been discussed in some studies as the result of the formation of a subscale silica layer in high Si content steels. Silicon concentrates in Laves phases within the steel, which are thermodynamically stable at low temperature [13]. At high temperatures, an oversaturation of Si in Laves phases can lead to the formation of a silica layer in the metal-oxide interface and create stresses [13]. However, this theory opposes the observed spallation at lower temperatures. On the other hand, it has also been proved that metal-oxide adhesion is favored by the presence of REs such as Ce [14]. The mechanisms of how Ce helps to reduce spallation have been researched elsewhere [15, 16]. It has been suggested that Ce limits ion diffusion in the Cr_2O_3 boundaries, reducing the effect of impurities and other defects. This could explain why spallation seems to be more

significant in the biggest exposed areas where Ce is not present, in combination with the substrate deformation effect.

The morphological evolution described for isothermal treatments applies as well for the isochronous treatments, regarding the volume expansion and the morphology of the oxides on the coating at different temperatures. However, it is known that thermal cycles in discontinuous treatments affect oxidation behavior [12]. In a sequence of isothermal treatments, the influence in short times is less significant as the treatments have the same contribution in the overall result. However, in isochronous treatments, the different diffusion temperatures can generate successive microstructural changes. Figure 3 f to h demonstrates that short treatment times of one hour did not allow a sufficient diffusion to create a homogeneous layer of oxides even at high temperatures. The longest 24-hour treatments at the other end only showed substantial healing at 850 °C (Figure 3 I). An explanation for this could be attributed to the diffculted element diffusion through the inner oxide layers formed at lower temperatures. The progression of the morphology in the 5-hour temperature series (Figure 3 f to h) also seems to agree with this idea, as the improvement of the self-healing properties seems to be very minimal despite the longer treatment times than the 1-hour series.

3.2. Chemical Development of the Self-Healing properties

From the image analysis, it was observed that the samples undergoing isothermal exposures at 750 and 850 °C showed a steady development of self-healing properties. In the isothermal 750 °C series, the as-formed composition is very similar to the specified composition for the steel grade (Figure 6 a). Increased exposure times allow for Mn diffusion to the top layer which generates a (Cr,Mn)₃O₄ spinel. Fe could also be present in the spinel, but its source is indiscernible from the contribution of the substrate to the total amount. The enrichment of Co, Cr and Mn in the crack surface (Figure 6 b) is in agreement with the observed results from other authors [6, 16]. The low amount of Mn detected in the analysis after 5 hours indicates that not enough time was given for diffusion. On the other hand, the increase of Co content at 24 hours (Figure 6 c) can be explained by the surface diffusion of the coating which was previously observed in Figure 24 I d) and observed from different sources [13, 16]. However, the crystallite formation in the crack surface would have resulted from the combination of Co with the Mn upward diffusion [16, 17].

Figure 6. Evolution of the chemical composition over time (0 h, 5 h, 24 h) for samples exposed at 750 °C

The increased temperature in the 850 °C series resulted in a faster obtention of the self-healing. The growth of this scale is much faster in high temperatures as the rate-limiting step for oxide growth is solid state diffusion, observed in the parabolic mass gain behavior by several authors [10, 16]. The increase in homogenization towards the end of the treatments which was observed by image analysis was confirmed by the chemical analysis. In the first hour, the crack was covered in (Co,Mn)₃O₄ and the Co was incorporated in substitutional solution (Figure 7). The Cr content in the crack increased

linearly as the chromia scale was formed, with a 10% increase from what was observed at 750 °C. Co content increased to more than twice the amount seen at 750 °C at 24 h due to surface diffusion, and higher Mn content was also observed. Both Co and Mn reached similar values in the analysis of the coating and the crack, which suggests that the formation of a $(\text{Co,Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ continuous layer was complete.

Figure 7. Evolution of the chemical composition over time (0 h, 5 h, 24 h) for samples exposed at 850 °C

4. Conclusions

The aim of the present study was to provide insight about how several pre-oxidation treatments influence the self-healing properties of the cracks generated in the material during the forming process.

It was observed that pre-oxidation temperature had a big impact on most morphological transformations of the coating and the substrate within the treatment times studied. Below 750 °C, the material would not develop significant signs of healing aside from the initial volume expansion. Moreover, the development of the self-healing properties of the oxide layer by alternative choices of isothermal or isochronous treatment design were observed. In particular, it was found that discontinuous isothermal treatments yielded a consistent evolution and homogenisation of the spinel oxides through the treatments compared to the isochronous series. This contrast was attributed to internal microstructural changes over the different temperatures.

Using EDS point analysis in exposed and coated areas, an advanced stage of self-healing was found in the 850 °C series after 24 hours. The formation of a cobalt spinel coating $(\text{Co,Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ over the Cr_2O_3 layer is observed. The 750 °C series also showed promising results, as the decreased temperature translated in a reduction of the Cr content, possibly indicating that a thinner chromia layer was formed. Nevertheless, Co oxides and Mn were found over coating and cracks allegedly reducing the rate of Cr evaporation.

Further work must be performed to find the relevance of the healing properties found in the general performance of the material. The experimental conditions in a box furnace are not able to reproduce some accelerate corrosion mechanisms in the operating conditions found in dual atmosphere [8] such as breakaway corrosion, which may differ significantly from the expected protective behavior of the oxide layer. Furthermore, the growth of the chromia scale and its effect on the conductivity would also needs to be investigated.

References

- [1] N. Shaigan, W. Qu, D. G. Ivey, W. Chen, "A review of recent progress in coatings, surface modifications and alloy developments for solid oxide fuel cell ferritic stainless steel interconnects," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 195, no. 6, pp. 1529-1542, 2010.
- [2] J. C.W. Mah, A. Muchtar, M. R. Somalu, M. J. Ghazali, "Metallic interconnects for solid oxide fuel cell: A review on protective coatings and deposition techniques" *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 14, pp. 9219-9229, 2017.

- [3] S. Fontana, R. Amendol, S. Chevalier, P. Piccardo, G. Caboche, M. Viviani, R. Molins, M. Sennour, "Metallic interconnects for SOFC: Characterisation of corrosion resistance and conductivity evaluation at operating temperature of differently coated alloys," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 171, no. 2, pp. 652-662, 2007.
- [4] Z. Yang, G.-G. Xia, X.-H. Li and J. W. Stevenson, "(Mn,Co)₃O₄ spinel coatings on ferritic stainless steels for SOFC interconnect applications," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 32, no. 16, pp. 3648-3654, 2007.
- [5] M. W. Lundberg, J. Westlinder, H. Holmberg, Robert Berger, "Self Healing Precoated AISI 441 for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Interconnects," *SMT R&D Surface Technology AB Sandvik Material Technology*, 2018.
- [6] E. Alvarez, A. Meier, K. Scott Weil, Zhenguang Yang, "Oxidation Kinetics of Manganese Cobaltite Spinel Protection Layers on Sanergy HT for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Interconnect Applications," *International Journal of Applied Ceramic Technology*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 33-41, 2011.
- [7] J. Froitzheim, S. Canovic, M. Nikuma, R. Sachitanand, L.G. Johansson, J.E. Svensson, "Long term study of Cr evaporation and high temperature corrosion behaviour of Co coated ferritic steel for solid oxide interconnects," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 220, pp. 217-227, 2012.
- [8] S. Fontana, S. Chevalier, G. Caboche. C. a. G. C. S. Fontana, "Metallic Interconnects for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell: Performance of Reactive Element Oxide Coating During 10, 20 and 30 Months Exposure," *Oxidation of Metals*, vol. 78, no. 5-6, pp. 307-328, 2012.
- [9] U. Bexell, M. Olsson and M. W. Lundberg, "High Temperature Oxidation of Plastically Deformed Ferritic Interconnect Steel," in *12th International Symposium on Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC)*, Montreal, 2011.
- [10] H. Falk Windisch, M. Sattari, J. E. Svensson and J. Froitzheim, "Chromium vaporization from mechanically deformed pre-coated interconnects in SOFC," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 297, pp. 217-223, 2015.
- [11] J. G. Grolig, "Coated Ferritic Stainless Steels as Interconnects in SOFC," PhD thesis. Chalmers University, Göteborg, Sweden 2015.
- [12] J. G. Grolig, J. Froitzheim and J. E. Svensson, "Coated Stainless Steel 441 as Interconnect Material for Solid Oxide Fuel Cells: Oxidation Performance and Chromium Evaporation," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 248, no. doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.08.089, pp. 1007-1013, 2014.
- [13] P. D. Jablonski, C. J. Cowen and J. S. Sears, "Exploration of alloy 441 chemistry for solid oxide fuel cell interconnect application," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 195, no. 3, pp. 813-820, 2010.
- [14] J. S. P.Y. Hou, "The effect of reactive element additions on the selective oxidation, growth and adhesion of chromia scales," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 202, no. 1-2, pp. 1-10, 1995.
- [15] S. Chevalier, "What did we learn on the reactive element effect in chromia scale since Pfeil's patent?," *Materials and Corrosion*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 109-115, 2014.
- [16] P. Guo, Y. Lai, Y. Shao, Y. Zhang, H. Sun and Y. Wang, "Oxidation Characteristics and Electrical Properties of Doped Mn-Co Spinel Reaction Layer for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Metal Interconnects," *Coatings*, vol. 42, no. 8, 2017.
- [17] P. Kofstad, *High Temperature Corrosion*, London: Elsevier Applied Science, 1988.

Keywords: EFCF2020, SOx

Session B13: Cells, stacks, and interconnects

Remark: This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International